

Assessment of Physico-Chemical Characteristics of Water at Selected Stations of Mokuro Lake, Ile-Ife, Nigeria

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Abstract

Water bodies are essential components of the environment and provide various ecological services to humans and wildlife. The quality of water is influenced by natural and anthropogenic factors. This study investigated physico-chemical characteristics of Mokuro Lake, a vital water resource for Ile-Ife community. Water samples were collected from six sampling stations once every three months from February 2020 to November 2021 to cover the two major seasons of the year. Temperature, electrical conductivity, and pH were measured in situ. Total dissolved solids (TDS) were estimated using a gravimetric method. Dissolved oxygen, BOD₅, total acidity, total alkalinity, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, and Cl⁻ were analyzed using volumetric methods. NO₃⁻ and PO₄³⁻ were determined using spectrophotometric technique, SO₄²⁻ was determined using the turbidimetric method, while flame emission spectrophotometry was used to determine Na⁺ and K⁺. Data obtained were statistically analyzed using standard methods. The results showed that electrical conductivity and turbidity showed significant difference ($p < 0.05$) across the sampling stations. Seasonal variations showed very highly significant differences ($p < 0.001$) in temperature, pH, acidity, TDS, PO₄³⁻, and K⁺; highly significant differences ($p < 0.01$) in conductivity, Mg²⁺, SO₄²⁻, and BOD₅ and significant variation ($p < 0.05$) in chloride ion. Physico-chemical parameters of Mokuro Lake were within WHO and NIS permissible limits for drinking water except for turbidity that fell above the limits. However, regular monitoring and control of industrial and agricultural activities around the lake is required. Increased public education is needed to promote sustainable use and conservation of Mokuro Lake.

Keywords: Water, physico-chemical parameters, lake, seasonal variation, freshwater ecosystem.

INTRODUCTION

Water is an indispensable resource, vital for sustaining life and supporting the functioning of natural ecosystems and human activities such as agriculture, industry, and domestic use (Haque et al., 2019; WHO, 2023). However, population growth, urbanization, and industrialization have led to increased pressure on freshwater resources, resulting in widespread contamination of water bodies. In its natural state, water often contains chemical, physical, and biological constituents that may impair its suitability for specific uses. Water pollution is defined as any chemical, biological, or physical change that harms living organisms or renders water unusable (Iyama et al., 2014, Mahala, 2024). According to WHO (2023), up to 80% of diseases

in developing nations are linked to unsafe water, emphasizing the importance of water quality monitoring. The physico-chemical properties of water, including temperature, pH, electrical conductivity, turbidity, dissolved oxygen (DO), biological oxygen demand (BOD), total dissolved solids (TDS), and major ions, are essential indicators of water quality and ecosystem health. Variations in these parameters are often influenced by seasonal changes and anthropogenic inputs such as agricultural runoff, industrial effluents, and domestic waste (Rahman et al., 2021). Recent studies in parts of Nigeria, such as Oyo and Lagos States, have reported declining water quality due to agricultural activities and unregulated discharges (Bilewu, 2022), highlighting the urgent need for regular assessment and protection of freshwater bodies.

Mokuro Lake, located in Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria, serves as a key freshwater resource for surrounding communities. It supports a range of domestic and agricultural uses, making its quality crucial for public health and local development. The lake receives inflow primarily from the Mokuro stream, which originates from Ora Hill, and is bordered by farmlands that may contribute pollutants through surface runoff. Despite its importance, Mokuro Lake remains under-researched, with limited empirical data on its water quality, especially in terms of spatial and seasonal variations.

This study addresses this knowledge gap by conducting a comprehensive assessment of the physico-chemical properties of Mokuro Lake. The findings will provide baseline data for monitoring, contribute to water quality management strategies, and inform policymakers and stakeholders on potential threats and necessary interventions. Ultimately, this research aims to support sustainable water resource management in Ile-Ife and similar ecological settings.

METHODOLOGY

A. Study Area

This study was conducted at Mokuro Lake, located in Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria. The dam, which spans an area of approximately 1.6×10^{-3} km², is situated along Mokuro Road at the northeastern extension from Moore Road, opposite the Ife Police Station at Enuwa, and lies a few kilometres from the Nigerian Television Authority (NTA). Ile-Ife falls within Longitudes 004°27'22.5" and 004°35'40.61"E, and Latitudes 07°28'43.5" and 07°34'51.41"N. The lake is fed solely by Mokuro Stream, which originates from Ora Hill (Petters and Odeyemi, 1985). Surrounding the dam are arable farmlands on the right and a cocoa plantation on the left. Mokuro Lake serves as a crucial water source for Ile-Ife and its neighbouring communities, providing piped water to residents along Mokuro Road and supporting both domestic and commercial water needs. To evaluate its water quality, 24 samples were collected quarterly from six stations across the lake between February 2020 and November 2021, covering both wet and dry seasons. The sampling stations included: station 1 (eastern part of the lake “the dam site”), 2 (southern part “a riverine area”), 3 (western part, “littoral 1”), 4 (central part “open water”), 5 (north western part “littoral 2”) and 6 (northeastern part, “littoral zones 3”) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Map of Nigeria showing Osun State and the Study Area

B. Field Determinations and Physico-chemical Analysis

Water temperature, electrical conductivity and pH were measured in situ using a thermometer, and a combo meter respectively after proper probe rinsing. The samples for the determination of dissolved oxygen (DO) were collected in 250/125 ml capacity glass reagent bottles, fixed in the field using Winkler's reagents, and analyzed in the laboratory by titration using Winkler's method. BOD₅ samples were equally collected in dark glass reagent bottles but were fixed. Biological oxygen demand (BOD) water samples were kept in a dark cupboard at room temperature (25 °C) for five days after which the oxygen content was determined titrimetrically (Ademoroti, 1996). Turbidity was determined nephelometrically at 540 nm. Total dissolved solids (TDS) were estimated gravimetrically after evaporation at 105°C. Alkalinity and acidity were determined by acid-base titration using appropriate indicators. Calcium and magnesium were quantified via EDTA titration, with magnesium derived by difference. Sodium and potassium were measured by flame emission spectrophotometry. Chloride was determined using Mohr titration, sulphate by turbidimetry with barium chloride, and nitrate and phosphate by colorimetric methods using brucine and stannous chloride/molybdenum-antimony reagents, respectively (APHA et al., 1995). The physico-chemical parameters assessed in this study were selected because they represent key indicators of water quality and ecosystem health. Parameters such as temperature, pH, electrical conductivity, and TDS reflect the ionic composition of the aquatic system. Dissolved oxygen and BOD₅ indicate organic-matter decomposition and oxygen availability, while nutrients (nitrate, phosphate) reveal eutrophication potential. Major ions and alkalinity describe buffering capacity and mineral characteristics. Together these variables give a comprehensive picture of both natural variability and human influence on Mokuro Lake.

C. Data Analysis

Data collected were subjected to inferential statistical analysis and Analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the physico-chemical variations across the sampling stations and T-tests was used to determine the seasonal variations using SPSS 25 version.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tables 1 and 2 summarize the variations in the spatial and seasonal mean values (Mean \pm S.E) of the physico-chemical parameters of Mokuro Lake. Temperature is one of the major physico-chemical parameters used to assess water quality for human consumption (Rahman et al. (2021). In this study, water temperature showed a homogeneous distribution across sampling

Table 1: Variations in the Mean value (Mean \pm S.E) of Physico-chemical Parameters investigated in each Station of Mokuro Lake, Ile-Ife during the Period of Study

Parameters	1	2	3	4	5	6	Over all Mean	F	P	WH O 201 7	NIS 200 7	
Water Temperature(°C)	27.38 ± 1.38	27.8 ± 1.44	27.95 ± 1.54	26.87 ± 1.56	27.73 ± 1.55	27.20 ± 1.50	27.50 ± 0.54	0.079	0.10	<40	<40	
Turbidity (NTU)	11.83 ± 4.35	± 9.83	8.11 ± 3.35	14.26 ± 0.94	8.43 ± 1.99	± 4.19	± 1.61	2.70	2	0.05*	5	5
pH	7.43 ± 0.05	± 0.08	7.31 ± 0.13	7.03 ± 0.13	7.30 ± 0.05	± 0.29	7.22 ± 0.06	2.00	5	0.13	6.5-8.5	6..5-8.5
Conductivity (uScm-1)	194.25 ± 7.16	195.00 ± 7.67	194.2 ± 7.42	200.75 ± 6.88	195.0 ± 7.72	238.2 ± 17.57	202.9 ± 4.87	3.15	8	0.03*	100	100
Total Acidity (mg/L)	33.50 ± 10.34	17.3 ± 5	50.00 ± 22.42	58.50 ± 18.64	39.50 ± 15.90	55.0 ± 18.12	47.17 ± 6.57	0.29	0	0.91	ND	ND
Total Alkalinity (mg/L)	79.00 ± 5.26	12.4 ± 0	87.00 ± 5.07	81.00 ± 6.25	87.50 ± 6.24	81.50 ± 5.12	82.50 ± 2.70	0.28	2	0.92	200	ND
Total Dissolved Solids (mg/L)	114.50 ± 7.41	113.50 ± 4.59	109.7 ± 3.64	113.75 ± 2.63	110.00 ± 3.37	135.2 ± 10.45	116.1 ± 2.84	2.54	2	0.07	500	500
Calcium (mg/L)	44.11 ± 17.52	11.5 ± 9	37.74 ± 12.13	42.09 ± 11.049	33.47 ± 6.25	37.17 ± 9.50	38.87 ± 4.33	0.10	2	0.10	75-200	ND
Magnesium (mg/L)	17.55 ± 6.21	6 ± 6.26	15.75 ± 5.92	18.20 ± 6.36	4.46 ± 28.19	4.88 ± 25.47	12.87 ± 25.41	0.02	4	>0.05	50	0.2
Sodium (mg/L)	22.31 ± 4.74	3 ± 6.10	26.90 ± 7.45	25.04 ± 5.35	± 7.02	± 6.26	± 2.28	0.10	6	0.99	200	200
Potassium (mg/L)	18.65 ± 8.89	8 ± 9.90	16.21 ± 6.33	17.17 ± 7.68	± 6.76	± 5.46	± 2.82	0.13	5	0.98	12	ND
Chloride (mg/L)	24.54 ± 6.31	3 ± 4.79	21.66 ± 4.34	26.45 ± 5.17	± 5.96	± 6.87	± 2.07	0.12	5	0.99	250	250
Sulphate (mg/L)	62.80 ± 19.59	35.6 ± 0	74.67 ± 24.70	59.53 ± 19.30	± 14.24	± 36.90	± 9.81	0.19	9	0.96	200	100
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	2.92 ± 0.16	3.75 ± 0.50	3.61 ± 0.750	3.14 ± 0.24	2.96 ± 0.15	± 0.56	± 0.79	2.41	2	0.08	5	5

Biological Oxygen Demand (mg/L)	0.50 ± 0.12	1.05 ± 0.44	0.80 ± 0.29	0.63 ± 0.34	4.93 ± 4.04	3.65 ± 3.12	1.93 ± 0.84	0.80	4	0.56	2-5	5
Nitrate (mg/L)	9.42 ± 3.54	9 ± 5.31	8.69 ± 3.13	10.27 ± 4.01	8.64 ± 3.10	± 3.43	± 1.40	0.06	9	1.00	50	50
Phosphate (mg/L)	1.09 ± 0.54	± 0.61	1.48 ± 0.78	0.82 ± 0.41	1.45 ± 0.74	± 0.01	± 0.22	0.20	6	0.96	ND	ND

*Significant ($p < 0.05$), ND = No Data, S.E. = Standard Error, mg/L= milligrams per Litre

Table 2: Seasonal Variations of Physico-chemical Parameters of the Water Quality in Mokuro Lake, Ile-Ife during the Period of Study

Parameters	SEASON		ANOVA	
	Wet Mean ± S. E n=12	Dry Mean ± S. E n=12	F	P
Water Temperature(°C)	25.33±0.22	29.66 ± 0.58	30.08	0.001***
Turbidity (NTU)	15.06 ± 1.36	10.04 ± 2.81	4.175	0.05*
pH	7.40 ± 0.03	7.04 ± 0.11	13.39	0.001***
Conductivity (µS/cm)	204.50 ± 1.19	201.33 ± 9.86	8.29	0.01**
Total Acidity (mg/L)	54.33 ± 11.98	40.00 ± 5.26	20.39	0.001***
Total Alkalinity (mg/L)	84.33 ± 4.05	80.67 ± 3.67	2.65	0.12
Total Dissolved Solids (mg/L)	114.83 ± 0.65	117.42± 5.73	16.34	0.001***
Calcium (mg/L)	21.50 ± 0.81	56.25 ± 4.79	15.14	0.001***
Magnesium (mg/L)	8.20 ± 0.72	26.13 ± 1.70	11.59	< 0.001
Sodium (mg/L)	15.13 ± 0.42	35.68 ± 1.54	3.34	0.08
Potassium (mg/L)	29.16 ± 2.08	4.04 ± 0.38	32.94	0.001***
Chloride (mg/L)	14.90 ± 0.52	32.60 ± 1.86	7.00	0.02*
Sulphate (mg/L)	104.71 ± 11.42	28.07 ± 2.32	12.90	< 0.001
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/L)	3.63± 1.58	3.93± 0.34	0.01	0.91
Biological Oxygen Demand(mg/L)	3.48 ± 1.58	0.37 ± 0.07	11.48	0.003**
Nitrate (mg/L)	15.89± 0.98	3.40 ± 0.30	2.24	0.15
Phosphate (mg/L)	2.16 ± 0.15	0.15 ± 0.01	31.64	0.001***

* Significant ($p < 0.05$) ** Highly significant ($p < 0.01$) *** Very highly significant ($p < 0.001$)
mg/L= milligrams per Litre

stations ($p > 0.05$), but varied significantly ($p < 0.001$) between seasons, with higher temperatures recorded in the dry season (29.66 ± 0.58 °C) and lower values in the wet season (25.33 ± 0.22 °C) (Table 1 and 2). The seasonal temperature variation reflects increased solar radiation during the dry season. Recorded temperatures were within WHO (2017) permissible limits.. The pH of water samples was relatively uniform across stations ($p > .05$), but significant seasonal variation was noted, with higher pH values observed in the wet season ($p < 0.001$). This could be attributed to the dilution effect of rainwater and enhanced biological activity during the wet period. The pH values, ranging from slightly acidic to alkaline, fell within the acceptable limits for drinking water (NIS, 2007; WHO, 2017). These findings are in agreement with the study of Chui et al. (2023) on River Njoro and Lake Nakuru in Kenya. Turbidity exhibited significant spatial variation ($p < 0.05$), with Station 6 (littoral 3) consistently recording higher turbidity values (22.86 ± 4.19 NTU) compared to other stations (ranging from 8.11 ± 3.35 to 14.26 ± 0.94 NTU). The elevated turbidity at Station 6 suggests a localized source of suspended materials, possibly from sediment resuspension or runoff (Table 1). Seasonally, turbidity was significantly higher in the wet season (15.06 ± 1.36 NTU) than in the dry season (10.04 ± 2.81 NTU) ($p < 0.05$), (Table 2) likely due to increased runoff carrying sediments into the water body. An integrated examination of spatial and seasonal variations shows that environmental pressures are unevenly distributed across Mokuro Lake. Station 6, which recorded the highest turbidity and lowest DO, lies in a littoral zone exposed to farmland runoff. During the wet season, rainfall and surface erosion intensify sediment inflow and organic loading, further increasing turbidity and lowering oxygen. This interaction demonstrates how hydrological seasonality amplifies localized pollution, making certain zones more vulnerable. Hence, both spatial heterogeneity and seasonal fluctuations jointly determine the lake's ecological health. These results are consistent with the findings of Nwankwoala and Ememu (2017), who also observed higher turbidity levels during wet seasons. Electrical conductivity showed significant spatial variation ($p < 0.05$), with Station 6 (Littoral zone 3) recording the highest value (238.25 ± 17.57 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), which may be linked to localized input of dissolved ions. Seasonally, conductivity was slightly higher in the wet season (204.50 ± 1.19 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) than in the dry season (201.33 ± 9.86 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) ($p < 0.01$), (Table 2) likely due to surface runoff introducing dissolved substances into the lake. The overall mean conductivity (202.92 ± 4.87 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) was lower than that reported by Adedeji et al. (2019), who found a mean conductivity of 432 ± 8.64 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. The increased conductivity, especially in the wet season, supports the notion of higher dissolved salts and nutrient loads in runoff (Kadir et al., 2019), which may affect aquatic life if prolonged. Total dissolved solids (TDS), calcium, magnesium, sodium, and chloride did not show significant spatial variation but exhibited higher concentrations in the dry season ($p < 0.05$). This is likely due to evaporation concentrating these substances during the dry season. The mean total dissolved solids (TDS) value in this study is consistent with findings from Adesakin et al. (2020) in Bomo river. The wide standard error observed for magnesium (17.17 ± 12.87 mg/L) suggests substantial spatial variability among the sampling stations, possibly reflecting differences in local geology, mineral dissolution, or runoff influence. However, Total dissolved solids (TDS), calcium, magnesium, sodium, and chloride are within WHO (2017) and NIS (2007) permissible limit for drinking water. In contrast, potassium, nitrate, and sulphate were higher in the wet season ($p < 0.05$), suggesting increased input from agricultural land runoff around the lake. However, nitrate did not show significant spatial or seasonal variation. Dissolved oxygen (DO) and biological oxygen demand (BOD) did not show significant spatial variation ($p > 0.05$). However, there's a notable difference in the mean dissolved oxygen, ranging from 2.26 ± 0.56 mg/L at station 6 to 3.75 ± 0.50 mg/L at station 2 (riverine area). The lower dissolved oxygen at station 6 (littoral zone 3) could be attributed to factors influencing high turbidity at the station 6. Seasonally, the mean value of DO was higher

in wet season than dry season. Temperature of water influences the amount of dissolved oxygen with only lesser oxygen dissolved in warm water than cold water (Nweke- Maraizu et al., 2023). Although, the DO values observed during this study period from the lake were within the WHO limits. Decreased in DO mean level observed in the river water samples may be due to fertilizer run offs from farmland..While low dissolved oxygen does not directly harm humans, it can lead to secondary water quality problems, such as the release of metals from bottom sediments and the formation of reduced compounds like hydrogen sulphides, which degrades water quality and affects aquatic organisms. BOD levels ranged widely, from 0.50 ± 0.12 mg/L at Station 1 (the dam site) to 4.93 ± 4.04 mg/L at Station 5 (littoral zone 2) (Table 1). The mean BOD did not vary significantly by station ($p > 0.05$) but was notably higher ($p < 0.01$) in the wet season, linked by Kadir et al. (2019) to agricultural and urban runoff. The relatively high BOD value (~ 5 mg/L) recorded at Station 5 indicates moderate organic pollution, implying increased microbial activity due to decomposable organic matter probably derived from domestic or agricultural sources. Such levels, although not extremely high, may reduce available oxygen for fish and benthic organisms, especially under warmer wet-season conditions when oxygen solubility decreases. Similarly, the low dissolved-oxygen concentrations observed at Station 6 coincide with high turbidity levels, suggesting that suspended particles limit light penetration and suppress photosynthetic oxygen production. This interaction results in hypoxic stress, which may restrict biodiversity to more tolerant species. Phosphate was also significantly higher ($p < 0.001$) in the wet season, suggesting fertilizer contamination from local farming. Total acidity was significantly higher in the wet season ($p < 0.001$) than dry season. Conversely, total alkalinity showed no significance across the stations or seasonal differences, aligning with the work of Olaoye & Olaniyan (2018) on River Kaduna (Table 1 and 2). Although most physico-chemical parameters of Mokuro Lake were within WHO (2017) and NIS (2007) permissible limits for drinking water, these thresholds focus on human health rather than ecosystem sustainability. From an ecological standpoint, the low dissolved-oxygen values (≈ 2.26 mg/L at Station 6) indicate hypoxic conditions that can reduce biodiversity and metabolic efficiency in aquatic fauna. High turbidity at the same station further limits photosynthesis and oxygen regeneration. Therefore, compliance with human standards does not necessarily imply ecological safety; monitoring programs should include ecological thresholds alongside public-health criteria.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study assessed the physico-chemical properties of Mokuro Lake in Ile-Ife, Nigeria, across six stations and over two seasons. The results revealed that while most parameters such as temperature, pH, TDS, DO, and major ions were within WHO (2017) and NIS (2007) permissible limits, certain parameters like turbidity exceeded recommended levels at Station 6 (littoral zone 3). Seasonal variation had a significant impact on most water quality parameters, with the wet season showing higher levels of turbidity, BOD, phosphate, potassium, and sulphate likely due to increased surface runoff and agricultural inputs. Spatially, Station 6 exhibited higher values in conductivity and turbidity, suggesting localized pollution sources.

The presence of agricultural runoff indicators during the wet season and elevated mineral concentrations during the dry season underscores the dual threats of seasonal flooding and evaporation. These findings highlight the vulnerability of Mokuro Lake to anthropogenic pressures, particularly from surrounding agricultural activities and land use patterns.

It is recommended that regular monitoring of Mokuro Lake is essential to detect changes in water quality over time. Buffer zones should be established to reduce agricultural runoff into the lake. Public education campaigns are needed to promote sustainable water use. Enforcement of environmental regulations will help control pollution sources.

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